

BRIEF REPORT

Tagus River microbial profile through nanopore sequencing on samples gathered from Prainha do Braco de Prata, Lisbon

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Cristiano Pedroso-Roussado ¹, Mariana Pestana¹, Ricardo Dias^{2,3},
Mónica Nunes³, Pedro Pascoal ³, Marcelo Pereira², Nuno Nunes¹

¹ITI/LARSyS, Universidade de Lisboa Instituto Superior Tecnico, Lisboa, Portugal²BioISI-Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute, Universidade de Lisboa Faculdade de Ciencias, Lisbon, Portugal³cE3c-Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes & CHANGE-Global Change and Sustainability Institute, Universidade de Lisboa Faculdade de Ciencias, Lisbon, Portugal

V1 First published: 29 Jul 2024, 4:155
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18072.1>
 Second version: 05 Dec 2024, 4:155
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18072.2>
 Latest published: 11 Apr 2025, 4:155
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18072.3>

Abstract

Background

Freshwater ecosystems play a vital role for humans and more-than-humans, and their study can elucidate their dynamic state throughout time. However, there is not much knowledge about the microbial profiles and their relevance for the ecosystem balance is still unclear.

Methods

In this Brief Report three freshwater samples collected in the Tagus River north margin were analysed through 16S-targeted nanopore sequencing and by customized bioinformatics pipeline.

Results

Our results revealed a consensual microbial profile with *Candidatus Pelagibacter*, *Egibacter*, and *Ralstonia* as the most abundant genera. Additionally, through a literature review we found that the ecosystem services provided by these genera are mostly related to organic matter decomposition.

Conclusions

Despite the need for a more robust sampling and analyses, we

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 3 (revision) 11 Apr 2025			
version 2 (revision) 05 Dec 2024		 view	
version 1 29 Jul 2024	 view		

1. **Dave R. Clark**, University of Essex,
Colchester,, UK

2. **Anyi Hu** , Chinese Academy of Sciences,
Xiamen, China

3. **Sushanta Deb** , Chinese Academy of
Sciences, Xiamen, China

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

conclude that there is potential to use microbial profile approaches to help define the relevant microbial biomarkers to clarify the ecosystem services in the Tagus River freshwater ecosystem.

Plain Language Summary

Water is life and its quality is important to the natural balance. In this Brief Report we studied three water samples collected in the Tagus River, near Beato and found that *Candidatus Pelagibacter*, *Egibacter*, and *Ralstonia* were the most abundant microbes detected. During our search for the role these microbes have in the river we concluded that there is not enough information about them. From what we observed, they are related to decompose organic matter, but there is a need to analyse more samples to have a clearer picture about the microbiology of the Tagus River.

Keywords

Tagus River, Freshwater microbiota, Nanopore sequencing, Microbiota, Lisbon

This article is included in the [Horizon Europe](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

Corresponding author: Cristiano Pedroso-Roussado (cristiano.roussado@tecnico.ulisboa.pt)

Author roles: **Pedroso-Roussado C:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Pestana M:** Funding Acquisition, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Dias R:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization; **Nunes M:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization; **Pascoal P:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization; **Pereira M:** Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization; **Nunes N:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [952226] (Enhancing the research and innovation potential of Técnico through Blockchain technologies and design Innovation for social Good [BIG]) and from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [101079995] (Bauhaus of the Seas Sails [BoSS]). This project has also received funding from the PRR (Plano de Recuperação e Resiliência português) under grant agreement No 02-C05-i01.01-2022.PC645022399-00000057 (eGames Lab), from the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia under grant agreement No UIDB/50009/2020 (ITI/LARSyS) and from the Porto Design Biennale. *The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.*

Copyright: © 2024 Pedroso-Roussado C *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Pedroso-Roussado C, Pestana M, Dias R *et al.* **Tagus River microbial profile through nanopore sequencing on samples gathered from Prainha do Braco de Prata, Lisbon [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2024, 4:155 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18072.1>

First published: 29 Jul 2024, 4:155 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18072.1>

Introduction

A complete comprehension of the Tagus River ecosystem is lacking. Due to the transboundary relevance of the Tagus River, its comprehension is paramount. Moreover, there is also insufficient information about the present and future impact posed by challenges in water management (Sondermann & de Oliveira, 2022), by climate change (Sondermann & de Oliveira, 2022), and anthropogenic alterations (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020).

In terrestrial ecosystems most biomass comes from plants, where microbial biomass accounts for ~70% in the ocean (Bar-On *et al.*, 2018). Microorganisms have short lifecycles and large population size so their organization and structure correspond to a swift adaptation to the shifting environmental changes (Cavan *et al.*, 2019; Collins *et al.*, 2014; Hellweger *et al.*, 2014). The global climate crisis is pressing the changes in marine ecosystems threatening the services they provide. This happens by major variations in the species present in marine habitats. To assess such fast shifts unified frameworks need to be developed that uses data from ecology, metabolism, and climate change (Baltar *et al.*, 2019). Without this knowledge, the ability to understand, evaluate, and forecast the future of marine communities, ecosystems, and their services is almost inefficient.

In this Brief Report we wanted to elucidate the microbial profile of a coastline location in the Tagus River estuary (Beato, Lisboa), and infer the potential causes and consequences of the presence of the observed taxa.

Methods

Samples collection

The environmental water samples were collected in Praínha de Braço de Prata (Figure 1). Three water samples were collected using three sterile plastic containers (5 L) for microbiota analysis. The containers were submerged at 0.5 meters and opened below surface to guarantee no air-borne microorganisms' collection.

Analytical workflow

The microbiota characterization was performed through characterization of 16S rRNA region of environmental DNA. The samples of this study had been analysed by a customized analytical pipeline developed by BioISIGenomics Research Group (Lisbon, Portugal) for long-read targeted nanopore sequencing in order to obtain high-accuracy taxonomical classification. The used approach had been validated through ZymoBIOMICS™ Microbial Community Standard (Zymo Research, USA) and sequencing runs were carried out on the GridION X5® (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK) sequencing platform. Sequencing data was obtained from 16S amplicons, low quality reads were removed and the remaining reads were size selected (keeping reads with lengths longer than 1200 bps and shorter than 1700 base pairs) using *prinseq-lite* (Schmieder & Edwards, 2011). Taxonomic classification was performed using a Lowest Common Ancestor approach: indexing based on on k-mers mapping to the lowest common ancestor of all genomes known to contain a given k-mer (Wood *et al.*, 2019). Following classification, data were rarefied and subjected to determination of taxa abundance (with a genera prevalence cutoff of ≥ 0.01) (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019).

Results

Nanopore sequencing general output

The three samples showed similar quality parameters which gives confidence that the sample collection and the sequencing approach were appropriately performed (Table 1). Specifically, the mean read length is equal in the three analyses (1,570-1,574 bases), the same for the mean read quality (Q = 17.7-18.0), and the percentage of reads above the cutoffs. The sample 2 produced less reads (and bases) than the other two samples, but that did not hamper the quality of the output.

Praínha de Braço de Prata microbiota

The top main phylum, genus, and species observed in the three water samples are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. Sample collection site - 'Praínha de Braço de Prata'. Left: aerial view map of the site (red arrow). Right: photo of the site taken in May 2020 by Miguel Silva. Google Maps (n.d.) (View from Praínha de Braço de Prata). Retrieved in July 13, 2023, from <https://www.google.com/maps/place/38°44'45.9%22N+9°05'47.2%22W/>.

Table 1. Main nanopore sequencing quality parameters from the three environmental samples.

Quality feature (units)	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Total number of reads (thousand)	>534	>339	>474
Total number of classified reads (%)	99.82	99.87	99.91
Total number of bases (million)	>841	>533	>746
Mean read length (bases)	1,574	1,570	1,571
Read length N50 (bases)	1,594	1,584	1,582
Mean read quality (Q score)*	17.5	18.0	18.0
Reads above quality 7 cutoff (%)	100.0	100.0	100.0
Reads above quality 10 cutoff (%)	100.0	100.0	100.0
Reads above quality 15 cutoff (%)	84.1	84.3	84.7

* Q score of 7 means a basecall accuracy of 80%, Q score of 10 means a basecall accuracy of 90%, and a Q score of 15 means an accuracy of 96.8%

Table 2. Three top phylum, genera, and species identified in the three samples with their respective relative abundance.

Sample	Rank	Taxa (relative abundance, %)
1	Phylum	<i>Pseudomonadota</i> (36), <i>Actinomycetota</i> (10), <i>Bacteroidota</i> (11)
	Family	<i>Flavobacteriaceae</i> (10), <i>Roseobacteraceae</i> (10), <i>Egibacteraceae</i> (7)
	Genus	<i>Egibacter</i> (7), <i>Tateyamaria</i> (6), <i>Ralstonia</i> (6)
	Species	<i>Egibacter rhizosphaerae</i> (7), <i>Tateyamaria omphalii</i> (6), <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (6)
2	Phylum	<i>Pseudomonadota</i> (65), <i>Actinomycetota</i> (15), <i>Bacteroidota</i> (15)
	Family	<i>Burkholderiaceae</i> (14), <i>Roseobacteraceae</i> (14), <i>Flavobacteriaceae</i> (13)
	Genus	<i>Ralstonia</i> (14), <i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> (11), <i>Egibacter</i> (10)
	Species	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (14), <i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> sp. (11), <i>Egibacter rhizosphaerae</i> (10)
3	Phylum	<i>Pseudomonadota</i> (45), <i>Actinomycetota</i> (13), <i>Bacteroidota</i> (10)
	Family	<i>Pelagibacteraceae</i> (17), <i>Egibacteraceae</i> (10), <i>Flavobacteriaceae</i> (9)
	Genus	<i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> (17), <i>Egibacter</i> (10), <i>Ralstonia</i> (7)
	Species	Uncultivated bacterium from the SAR86 clade (16), <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (10), <i>Egibacter rhizosphaerae</i> (7)

In order to assess the Praína do Braço de Prata microbiota we qualified and quantified the shared taxa between the three samples (Table 3).

Ecosystem services

Based on the shared taxa found between the three samples we used the top three genus and species to assess in PubMed database studies that inform the potential ecosystem services these taxa might be performing in the Tagus River. In total it was identified 17 articles related to *Pelagibacter* gen. and *Pelagibacter* sp., and 37 related to *Ralstonia* gen. and *Ralstonia solanacearum*. No article was found for *Egibacter* or *Egibacter rhizosphaerae*. Additionally, no review article was published about the ecosystem services of these taxa in the defined period

of search in the systematic analysis. The relevant articles found follow as: 14 for *Pelagibacter* gen. and *Pelagibacter* sp., and 11 for *Ralstonia* gen. and *R. solanacearum* (Table 4).

Conclusion

Rivers present a key importance for human life and for nature balance since it is the primordial source of renewable water (Vörösmarty *et al.*, 2010). However, there is a lack of studies that focus the microbial diversity in rivers compared to marine or lake ecosystems that could elucidate about its relevance for urban areas and ecosystems services. The dynamic flow of water and nutrients in rivers make their study complex but necessary to answer foundational questions regarding land

Table 3. Shared taxa at the phylum, family, genus, and species level between the three samples. Only the taxa with relative abundances above 10% are shown.

Rank	TaxaID (Relative Frequency, %)
Phylum	<i>Pseudomonadota</i> (61)
	<i>Actinomycetota</i> (17)
	<i>Bacteroidota</i> (16)
Family	<i>Flavobacteriaceae</i> (16)
	<i>Pelagibacteraceae</i> (15)
	<i>Roseobacteraceae</i> (14)
	<i>Egibacteraceae</i> (13)
	<i>Burkholderiaceae</i> (12)
Genus	<i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> (15)
	<i>Egibacter</i> (14)
	<i>Ralstonia</i> (12)
Species	<i>Egibacter rhizosphaerae</i> (14)
	<i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> sp. FZCC0015 (14)
	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (12)

Table 4. Relevant ecosystem services present in literature for the most abundant taxa.

TaxaID	Relevant reference	Ecosystem service/ phenotype
<i>Candidatus Pelagibacter</i> or SAR11	Rivers et al., 2013	Re-establishing the pre-oil spill microbial community structure.
	Tsementzi et al., 2019	Oligotrophy; auxotrophy for reduced sulfur (lacking a sulfite oxidase); differential phage predation and/or adaptation (fine tuning) of core genes to environmental conditions (e.g. temperature).
	Liu et al., 2023	Resistance to salinity; ability to grow in low nutrients sites (like dissolved inorganic nitrogen); utilizers of dissolved organic carbon.
	Han et al., 2020	Heterotrophy; carbon cycling; generalista; dimethylsulfoniopropionate degradation.
	Cerro-Gálvez et al., 2021	Oligotrophy; antitoxicity strategies (to anthropogenic dissolved organic carbon; high tolerance to hydrophobic chemicals)
	Chun et al., 2021	‘Skeleton’-formation and participate in species-engineered microenvironments; dominant in surface waters under stratified summer conditions; fine-tuning microbial modular structures; present in the nanoparticle-associated fraction; nitrate reduction, nitrification, dark sulfide oxidation.
	Delpech et al., 2021	Oligotrophy; follow; abundant in low nutrient concentrations and in stratified surface waters phytoplankton blooms
	Sun et al., 2021	Able to maximize nutrients uptake even when in low concentrations.
	Zhang et al., 2022	Present in anticyclonic eddies, in warmer surface water temperatures, where there is less diverse bacterial communities; oligotrophy; survives at lower salinity and chlorophyll a concentrations but tolerate higher concentrations.
	Anderson & Harvey, 2022	Oligotrophy; rely on copiotrophs to assimilate sources of carbon and other metabolites.
	Fortin et al., 2022	Predominant in <i>Alexandrium</i> sp. blooms; present in the particle-attached fraction of the surface water.
	Guo et al., 2022	Involved in nitrogen and/ or sulfur cycling: prevalent in oxygen-rich surface oceans
	Larkin et al., 2023	Heterotrophy; partition marine niche spaces; adapted to regions with low inorganic nitrogen supply; reveals habitat-specific partitioning in replication strategies for surface ocean communities
Sun et al., 2023	Prefers nitrogen-containing carbohydrates, oligo-glucans, oligo-cellulose, and lignin-derived aromatic fragments; polysaccharide degradation; scavenging mode in free-living fractions for the assimilation of dissolved carbohydrates, oligotrophy; key in significant flux of dissolved organic carbon and nutrient mineralization at the bottom of watery ecosystems.	

TaxaID	Relevant reference	Ecosystem service/ phenotype
Ralstonia	Coll <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Degradation of contaminants (e.g., organic pollutants);
	Rasool <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Tolerance to heavy metals like thallium; role in distributing metals; dominant in midstream soil samples; tent to enrich in bank of steam soils
	Chang <i>et al.</i> , 2021	Rare pathogenicity and transmitted through polluted waters.
	Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2023	Degrade microcystins; may enhance host-resistance to toxic cyanobacterial stress by affecting the whole bacterial community.
	Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2023a	May utilize diesel-derived organic intermediates produced by hydrocarbon degraders.
	Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2023b	Thrive in soil discharge and plant decomposition conditions; decomposition of several aromatic hydrocarbons.
<i>R. solanacearum</i>	Planas-Marquès <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Vascular pathogen; wide geographic distribution; colonizes many hosts, persists in soil and water for long periods; moves horizontally through the xylem ring by degrading the cell wall of primary xylem or pit membranes in the secondary xylem vessels.
	Biosca <i>et al.</i> , 2021	Infects ornamental plants; lytic lifestyle.
	Wen <i>et al.</i> , 2023	Cause wilt disease; affects the composition and diversity of rhizosphere microbiome

use and novel threats like antimicrobial resistance and the emergence of invasive species (Reddington *et al.*, 2020; van Rossum *et al.*, 2015). Despite the low number of samples analysed through this Brief Report, it is clear that we have insufficient information about the taxonomy of the most abundant taxa detected like *Pelagibacter* and *Egibacter* and more research is necessary to shed light on their relevant phenotypes aiming a better comprehension of the Tagus River ecosystem.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

BioProject Data Bank: 16S rRNA genomic data from the analyses of freshwater samples collected in Praínha do Braço de

Prata (Lisbon, Portugal). Accession number: PRJNA1116853; <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/?term=PRJNA1116853>; available in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (Pedroso-Roussado *et al.*, 2024).

Contributorship CRediT statement

Cristiano Pedroso-Roussado: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Mariana Pestana:** Validation, Writing – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. **Ricardo Dias:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Mónica Nunes:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Pedro Pascoal:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Marcelo Pereira:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Nuno Nunes:** Validation, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

References

- Anderson SR, Harvey EL: **Estuarine microbial networks and relationships vary between environmentally distinct communities.** *PeerJ.* 2022; **10**: e14005.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Baltar F, Bayer B, Bednarsek N, *et al.*: **Towards integrating evolution, metabolism, and climate change studies of marine ecosystems.** *Trends Ecol Evol.* 2019; **34**(11): 1022–1033.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bar-On YM, Phillips R, Milo R: **The biomass distribution on Earth.** *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2018; **115**(25): 6506–6511.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Biosca EG, Català-Senent JF, Figàs-Segura À, *et al.*: **Genomic analysis of the first European bacteriophages with depolymerase activity and biocontrol efficacy against the phytopathogen *Ralstonia solanacearum*.** *Viruses.* 2021; **13**(12): 2539.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Bolyen E, Rideout JR, Dillon MR, *et al.*: **Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible microbiome data science using QIIME 2.** *Nat Biotechnol.* 2019; **37**(8): 852–857.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Cavan EL, Henson SA, Boyd PW: **The sensitivity of subsurface microbes to ocean warming accentuates future declines in particulate carbon export.** *Front Ecol Evol.* 2019; **6**: 230.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Cerro-Gálvez E, Dachs J, Lundin D, *et al.*: **Responses of coastal marine microbiomes exposed to anthropogenic dissolved organic carbon.** *Environ Sci Technol.* 2021; **55**(14): 9609–9621.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Chang CJ, Zhang J, Tsai YL, *et al.*: **Compositional features of distinct microbiota base on serum Extracellular Vesicle metagenomics analysis in moderate to severe psoriasis patients.** *Cells.* 2021; **10**(9): 2349.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Chun SJ, Cui Y, Baek SH, *et al.*: **Seasonal succession of microbes in different size-fractions and their modular structures determined by both macro- and micro-environmental filtering in dynamic coastal waters.** *Sci Total Environ.* 2021; **784**: 147046.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Coll C, Bier R, Li Z, *et al.*: **Association between aquatic micropollutant dissipation and river sediment bacterial communities.** *Environ Sci Technol.* 2020; **54**(22): 14380–14392.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Collins S, Rost B, Rynearson TA: **Evolutionary potential of marine**

- phytoplankton under ocean acidification. *Evol Appl.* 2014; **7**(1): 140–155.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Delpech LM, Vonnahme TR, McGovern M, et al.: Terrestrial inputs shape coastal bacterial and archaeal communities in a high Arctic fjord (Isfjorden, Svalbard). *Front Microbiol.* 2021; **12**: 614634.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Fernandes MR, Aguiar FC, Martins MJ, et al.: Long-term human-generated alterations of tagus river: effects of hydrological regulation and land-use changes in distinct river zones. *CATENA.* 2020; **188**: 104466.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fortin SG, Song B, Anderson IC, et al.: Blooms of the harmful algae *margalefidinium polykrikoides* and *alexandrium monilatum* alter the York River estuary microbiome. *Harmful Algae.* 2022; **114**: 102216.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Guo R, Ma X, Zhang J, et al.: Microbial community structures and important taxa across oxygen gradients in the Andaman Sea and eastern Bay of Bengal epipelagic waters. *Front Microbiol.* 2022; **13**: 1041521.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Han D, Kang HY, Kang CK, et al.: Seasonal mixing-driven system in estuarine-coastal zone triggers an ecological shift in bacterial assemblages involved in phytoplankton-derived DMSP degradation. *Microb Ecol.* 2020; **79**(1): 12–20.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hellweger FL, Van Sebille E, Fredrick ND: Biogeographic patterns in ocean microbes emerge in a neutral agent-based model. *Science.* 2014; **345**(6202): 1346–1349.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Larkin AA, Hagstrom GI, Brock ML, et al.: Basin-scale biogeography of *prochlorococcus* and SAR11 ecotype replication. *ISME J.* 2023; **17**(2): 185–194.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Liu H, Yang X, Yang W, et al.: Gut microbiota of freshwater gastropod (*bellamya aeruginosa*) assist the adaptation of host to toxic cyanobacterial stress. *Toxins (Basel).* 2023; **15**(4): 252.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Pedroso-Roussado C, Pestana M, Dias R, et al.: Tagus river bacterial microbiota found in praina do braco de prata. *Sequence Read Archive.* Retrieved July 4, 2024 from 2024.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1116853/>
- Planas-Marqués M, Kressin JP, Kashyap A, et al.: Four bottlenecks restrict colonization and invasion by the pathogen *ralstonia solanacearum* in resistant tomato. *J Exp Bot.* 2020; **71**(6): 2157–2171.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Rasool A, Nasim W, Xiao T, et al.: Microbial diversity response in thallium polluted riverbank soils of the Lanmuchang. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf.* 2020; **187**: 109854.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Reddington K, Eccles D, O'Grady J, et al.: Metagenomic analysis of planktonic riverine microbial consortia using nanopore sequencing reveals insight into river microbe taxonomy and function. *GigaScience.* 2020; **9**(6): g1aa053.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Rivers AR, Sharma S, Tringe SG, et al.: Transcriptional response of bathypelagic marine bacterioplankton to the Deepwater Horizon oil spill. *ISME J.* 2013; **7**(12): 2315–2329.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Schmieder R, Edwards R: Quality control and preprocessing of metagenomic datasets. *Bioinformatics.* 2011; **27**(6): 863–864.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Sondermann MN, De Oliveira RP: Climate adaptation needs to reduce water scarcity vulnerability in the Tagus River basin. *Water.* 2022; **14**(16): 2527.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Sun FL, Wang YS, Wu ML, et al.: Bacterial community variations in the South China Sea driven by different chemical conditions. *Ecotoxicology.* 2021; **30**(9): 1808–1815.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Sun CC, Zhao WJ, Yue WZ, et al.: Polymeric carbohydrates utilization separates microbiomes into niches: Insights into the diversity of microbial carbohydrate-active enzymes in the inner shelf of the Pearl River Estuary, China. *Front Microbiol.* 2023; **14**: 1180321.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Tsementzi D, Rodriguez-R LM, Ruiz-Perez CA, et al.: Ecogenomic characterization of widespread, closely-related SAR11 clades of the freshwater genus “*Candidatus Fonsibacter*” and proposal of *Ca. Fonsibacter lacus* sp. Nov. *Syst Appl Microbiol.* 2019; **42**(4): 495–505.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Van Rossum T, Peabody MA, Uyaguari-Diaz MI, et al.: Year-long metagenomic study of river microbiomes across land use and water quality. *Front Microbiol.* 2015; **6**: 1405.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Vörösmarty CJ, McIntyre PB, Gessner MO, et al.: Global threats to human water security and river biodiversity. *Nature.* 2010; **467**(7315): 555–561.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wen T, Xie P, Liu H, et al.: Tapping the rhizosphere metabolites for the prebiotic control of soil-borne bacterial wilt disease. *Nat Commun.* 2023; **14**(1): 4497.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Wood DE, Lu J, Langmead B: Improved metagenomic analysis with Kraken 2. *Genome Biol.* 2019; **20**(1): 257.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Yang R, Peng C, Ye Y, et al.: Succession patterns of microbial composition and activity following the diesel spill in an urban river. *Microorganisms.* 2023b; **11**(3): 698.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Yang M, Wen G, Cao S, et al.: The formation of double metalimnetic oxygen minima in a drinking water reservoir and its influence on bacterial community. *Sci Total Environ.* 2023a; **860**: 160540.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhang W, Yuan W, Chen L, et al.: Uniqueness and dependence of bacterial communities on microplastics: comparison with water, sediment, and soil. *Microb Ecol.* 2022; **84**(4): 985–995.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 19 August 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19531.r42633>

© 2024 Hu A. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Anyi Hu

Institute of Urban Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Xiamen, China

This report employed the third-generation (nanopore) sequencing to profile the taxonomic composition of bacterial communities in three surface water samples of the Tagus River. *Candidatus Pelagibacter*, *Egibacter*, and *Ralstonia* were identified as the main bacterial taxa, which were proposed to play an important role in maintaining the river ecosystem service (e.g., organic matter decomposition).

This work is a preliminary descriptive study due to the limited sample size and shallow analysis. However, this report provided a snapshot for the taxonomic information of the planktonic bacterial communities in the Tagus River. Maybe in the future, more samples, more environmental variables and more advanced technologies (e.g., metagenomics) can be included into the Tagus River microbiome study.

I have a concern on the discussion about the ecosystem service of *Pelagibacter*. Since *Pelagibacter* is a typical marine bacteria, please carefully confirm whether the riverine bacteria is a marine one or the freshwater taxa who has a closed relationship with *Pelagibacter*. In addition, I think the current dataset and analysis of this report is hard to infer the ecosystem service provided by planktonic bacteria.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Aquatic microbial ecology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 13 August 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19531.r42629>

© 2024 Clark D. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Dave R. Clark

University of Essex, Colchester,, UK

The study by Pedroso-Roussado and colleagues characterises the microbial community structure of three water samples from the estuarine part of the Tagus River, Portugal. Although this is a low number of samples for a typical microbial ecology study, the authors have not over-interpreted their data nor conducted any under-powered statistical analysis. The authors report on the most abundant taxa detected, and infer their roles in organic matter degradation, highlighting the need for further data to better understand the role of understudied taxa. The study appears interesting, but some further basic information is required, particularly in the methods and results to provide further context.

Abstract:

Generally fine, but a few examples of odd / unclear phrases that may need revision. For instance, it is not clear what the authors mean by “Freshwater ecosystems play a vital role for humans and more-than humans”. If the authors mean that freshwater ecosystems are globally important, then it is better to say this in simple terms. It is also not clear what the authors mean by ‘consensual microbial profile’ – some re-wording is needed here.

Introduction:

Again, generally good, although it might have been nice to have a little more background on the Tagus River and why it is worthy of further study, as the introduction is a little too focussed on purely marine science rather than estuarine environments.

Methods:

There are some missing details on the molecular methods here. For example, how was DNA extracted from the samples? Were 16S genes amplified by PCR, if so, which primers?

Some additional details in the bioinformatics are also needed: "The used approach had been validated through ZymoBIOMICSTM Microbial Community Standard" – how was this approach validated and what data do the authors have to show this approach works? Also, to what sequencing depth were the samples rarefied to? Also, what steps are involved in this approach? At the moment, this methodology is not reproducible.

Results:

Again, there is some basic but interesting information about the samples missing. What was their diversity? How similar (beta diversity) were the samples to each other?

Also, whilst the literature search on ecosystem function was useful, why did the authors not use a bioinformatic tool to do this (e.g. PICRUST2 or similar)?

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Microbial community ecology, bioinformatics, statistical ecology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 25 Nov 2024

Cristiano Pedroso-Roussado

